

Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Effect on germination of presoaking dried sporocarps of *Azolla microphylla*

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Proliferation of azolla is largely through vegetative reproduction, but sexual reproduction also occurs. The sporophyte of azolla is heterosporous; both microsporocarp and megasporocarp are produced in the same plant.

We studied the effect on germination of presoaking dried frond-based sporocarps of *A. microphylla* in growth regulators. Dried sporocarps (5 g/treatment) were presoaked for 24 h in

2,4-D, kinetin, PcPA, GA₃, and NAA at 200 ppm and released into plastic tubs containing tap water. The numbers of young sporelings that germinated were recorded.

Table 1. Effect on germination of presoaking dried frond-based azolla sporocarps in growth regulators.

Growth regulator ^a (200 ppm)	Azolla sporelings germinated from megasporocarp ^b (av no.)	Increase over control (%)
Control	102 (19.5)	–
2,4-D	290 (73.7)	64
Kinetin	400 (55.4)	74
PcPA	400 (10.0)	73
GA ₃	410 (86.2)	75
NAA	240 (22.5)	56

^aFigures in parentheses are standard deviations. Each treatment used 5 g dried sporocarps for presoaking.

All the growth regulators stimulated germination of sporophyte (Table 1). Germination with GA₃, PcPA, and kinetin was higher.

In another study, sporocarps were presoaked in urea and potassium dihydrogen phosphate at 100 ppm for 24 h. Phosphate stimulated germination by 19%, urea inhibited it (Table 2). □

Table 2. Effect on germination of presoaking dried frond-based sporocarps in N and P.

Treatment ^a	Azolla sporelings germinated from megasporocarp ^b (av no.)	Difference from control (%)
Control	123.70 (15.5)	–
Nitrogen	67.30 (13.9)	–45.8
Phosphorus	152.00 (13.5)	+19.1

^a Each treatment used 5 g for presoaking. ^b Figures in parentheses are standard deviations.

Crop management

Effect of seed treatment on early seedling establishment under rainfed conditions

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We treated dry and water-imbibed seeds of Dular, 100-d rice variety, with 0.1% polyethylene glycol (PEG) solution to improve seedling vigor. The 1987 field trial at the IRRI farm was in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plot size was 6 m with 10 rows.

Descriptions of the six treatments are in the table. Plant height, tiller number, shoot dry weight, and leaf area were recorded 45 d after seeding (DAS).

Consistently high values of plant characteristics suggest that T6 is the best treatment.

Differences in osmotic concentration are developed during seed treatment with PEG: a seed is prevented from germination but not from imbibing a limited amount of water. That partial hydration allows the changes needed for rapid, synchronized germination and growth in water or soil. The osmotic concentration developed due to PEG treatment also restricts moisture loss in the seed or soil, improving early crop establishment.

Among the changes that some seeds develop during osmotic

concentration are activation of certain enzymes, such as esterases and acid phosphatases, that might participate in mobilization of seed reserves; improved capacity for the synthesis of RNA and protein presumably required for rapid cellular differentiation and growth; and decreased conductivity of leachates indicating repair and rearrangement of the cell membrane structure. In this study, improved mobilization of seed reserves and membrane repair might have increased seedling vigor. □

Characteristics of Dular variety as affected by six seed treatments.^a Karnataka, India.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Shoot dry weight (g)	Leaf area (cm ²)
T1 (dry seed)	57 c	109 c	36 c	2351 c
T2 (seed soaked 12 h in water)	58 bc	117 bc	43 c	2588 c
T3 (seed soaked 24 h in water)	63 ab	128 bc	55 b	3703 b
T4 (T1 + 0.1% PEG solution)	64 a	138 ab	57 b	3367 b
T5 (T2 + 0.1% PEG solution)	65 a	151 a	56 b	3863 ab
T6 (T3 + 0.1% PEG solution)	66 a	153 a	74 a	4246 a
CV (%)	5	9	7	9

^a In a column, means with the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b ** = significant at the 1% level, * = significant at the 5% level.